

EOSC Terminology

EOSC Association (EOSC-A)

EOSC-A is the legal entity established to represent the EOSC stakeholders in the **EOSC Co-programmed partnership** and to ensure coordination. It was set up in July 2020 as an international **non-profit organisation** under Belgian law with the aim to provide a single voice for advocacy and representation for the broader EOSC stakeholder community. It is the European Commission's partner in the EOSC co-programmed European partnership, whereby it co-develops the **EOSC Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda**. As of July 2025, it has 131 members, 97 observers, with 29 Mandated Organizations (256 in total).

EOSC EU Node

The vision for EOSC is to put in place a **system in Europe** to find and access data and services for research and innovation, to help researchers store, share, process, analyse and reuse FAIR research outputs within and across disciplines and borders. The architecture of EOSC is based on the concept of a **federation of nodes** implementing a system-of-system type architecture. The EOSC EU Node is the first node of the EOSC Federation, serving as a model for future nodes. It constitutes a European **multi-disciplinary and multi-national scientific data/service** portfolio for researchers and citizen scientists. Its practices and lessons learned will be shared with other nodes joining the EOSC Federation, contributing to resources like the **EOSC Federation Handbook**. It acts as one of the channels to bring services, data software, and all other kinds of research objects to the market, making them Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable for researchers. The EOSC EU Node has been procured by the European Commission and will be hosted and implemented by third-party sub-contractors.

EOSC Mandated Organisations

Mandated Organisations play a unique bi-directional role in the EOSC Association, representing **national interests** and coordinating input to and from their **respective constituencies**. Appointed by their governments, they are responsible for coordinating **policy alignment, fostering engagement, and facilitating communication** between EOSC-A and their respective communities. The unique role of Mandated Organisations is detailed in the Charter for Mandated Organisations, adopted at the EOSC Association's 4th General Assembly meeting in May 2022. The Member States and Associated Countries (MS/AC) are committed to supporting the **EOSC Partnership** among others by appointing Mandated Organisations (MOs) to EOSC-A, who are able to express views that represent the broader engagement and specificities of their respective national research system.

EOSC Association Task Forces

The **EOSC Association Task Forces**, together with the **EOSC Opportunity Area Expert Groups**, represent the EOSC brain pool. Together, these groups include hundreds of expert volunteers collectively working to develop key areas in the implementation of EOSC. In contrast to the OAEGs, which are **voluntary working groups**, Task Forces have a mandate to advise the **EOSC Association**.

EOSC Co-programmed partnership

EOSC has been granted special status as a co-programmed **European Partnership**. European Partnership status fortifies EOSC with European funding of **almost €500 million** and in-kind contributions of the partners of €500 million, with the aim of improving the storing, sharing and especially the combining and reusing of research data across borders and scientific disciplines. The Partnership brings together institutional, national and European initiatives and engages all relevant stakeholders to co-design and deploy a **European Research Data Commons** where data are **Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR)**.

EOSC Federation

The EOSC Federation will consist of multiple **EOSC Nodes** that are interconnected and can collaborate to share and manage **scientific data, knowledge, and resources** within and across thematic and geographical research communities. The EOSC Nodes will be **entry points for users** of the EOSC Federation, with each node offering its own (and possibly **third-party**) **services**, including data reposing and accessing services.

EOSC Federation Build-up Group

With the European Open Science Cloud quickly moving toward an operational EOSC Federation, the **EOSC Tripartite Governance** has established a process for the sequencing of the first wave of **Candidate EOSC Nodes**. The federating of the first thematic, national and organisational nodes with the EOSC EU Node will mark the start of the EOSC Federation. The Build-up Group has been established at the kick-off workshop of the EOSC Federation in March 2025, bringing together 13 candidate EOSC Node coordinators, the EOSC EU Node, two Group co-chairs, and observers from the European Commission, the EOSC Steering Board, and the EOSC Association Board. The Build-Up Group is steadily working toward the anticipated launch of the EOSC Federation at the EOSC Symposium in November 2025.

Multi-annual Roadmap (MAR)

The MAR constitutes Section 8 of the **SRIA** with the purpose of informing the periodically developed **Horizon Europe Work Programmes**. The EOSC Association regularly updates the MAR to devise a set of priority actions and outcomes for each upcoming Work Programme. The current MAR 2026-2027, as presented in SRIA 1.3, serves to inform the Horizon Europe Work Programme 2026-2027. Priorities are assigned to three levels for implementation: **European, National, and Institutional**.

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Opportunity Area Expert Groups

The EOSC Opportunity Area (OA) Expert Groups constitute a mechanism for collaboration on technical and related matters within the **Horizon Europe Co-programmed Partnership** for EOSC. They are a product of the voluntary collaboration across Horizon Europe (HE) EOSC-related projects, mainly in the domain of the **HE Technology Group**, and serve as the cornerstone of a **community of technical experts** collaborating to advance the development of EOSC. The **seven EOSC Opportunity Area Expert Groups** (as of July 2025) are designed to **maximize the impact** of the HE EOSC-related projects through strategic collaboration and co-creation of outputs with experts from the **EOSC-A Task Forces**. The concept was developed in the context of the planning for the first EOSC Winter School and was informed by clustering projects based on their contributions to EOSC according to the **SRIA Action Areas**. By facilitating collaboration within and outside the HE EOSC-related projects, OA Expert Groups generate significant added value by enhancing the broader community's ability to solve specific challenges in the development of EOSC. OA Expert Groups maintain dynamic work plans to accommodate the influx of new projects and members and meet the evolving needs of the EOSC community. Concrete collaborations include regular OA Expert Group meetings, routine presentations at meetings organised by the European Commission, the hosting of a joint session at the **EOSC Symposium** and developing the programme for the annual **EOSC Winter School** format.

Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA)

The SRIA defines the **general framework** for future research, development and innovation activities in relation to the European Open Science Cloud. This framework is subject to further development in the context of the EOSC Partnership, drawing on inputs from **EOSC Association member organizations**, **EOSC-A Task Forces**, and the **EOSC community** at large. The SRIA is used to inform the European Commission's work programmes via the **Multi-Annual Roadmap (MAR)**, which forms Section 8 of the SRIA. The current version of the SRIA, SRIA 1.3, including MAR 2026-2027, was approved by the EOSC Partnership Board in December 2024.

Vademecum

The Vademecum provides a **framework for the cooperation** between the **project consortia** funded through **EU Calls** supporting the EOSC European Co-Programmed Partnership ("the Partnership"), among themselves and with the EOSC Association ("EOSC-A"). The document has been **produced by EOSC-A**, after consultations with the European Commission's DG RTD, DG CNECT, and REA, in the spirit of helping project consortia to implement the **European Commission's terms and conditions** set out in the Work Programme 2021-2022, common to all Destination **INFRAEOSC projects** (and possibly other EC-funded projects that support EOSC) and that are or will be reflected in the Description of Action (DoA), annexed to the Grant Agreement. It complements the existing legal framework.

EOSC Rules of Participation (RoP)

The EOSC Rules of Participation state the **standard conduct** required of EOSC participants who are expected to adhere to the RoP to **build trust in the EOSC**. The former Rules of Participation Compliance Monitoring Task Force (RoP Task Force) worked on providing more **practical criteria** from the principles expressed in the current high-level EOSC RoP.

EOSC Tripartite Governance

The EOSC Tripartite Governance is a concept of **strategic coordination** between the **EU**, represented by the **European Commission**, the **EOSC Association**, and the **Member States and Associated Countries of the EOSC Steering Board**, to support the implementation of the **EOSC in Europe**, aligning national and EU policies to improve the production of **FAIR research outputs and advance Open Science**. The Tripartite Governance will ensure dialogue and strategic coordination of the policy implementation objectives of EOSC and its framework conditions as a pilot action to deepen the **European Research Area (ERA)**.

EOSC Winter School

The EOSC Winter School is an **in-person meeting format** conceived to increase cross-project alignment. Attendees include participants from the **EOSC-A Board and Secretariat**, the **European Commission**, the **HE EOSC-related projects**, the **OA Expert Groups**, and the **EOSC-A Task Forces**. The first EOSC Winter School was organised from 29 January-1 February 2024 in Thessaloniki, Greece, with close to 120 participants engaging in hands-on work to identify common challenges and collaboration opportunities, and a separate track on the sustainability of project outputs. The second Winter School took place from 20-23 January 2025 in Seville, Spain, with a focus on achieving convergence and supporting the build-up phase of the EOSC Federation.